

The Transaction: Your Day Reconfigured Through Swiss Historical Archive

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ABSTRACT

The Transaction is based on an intelligent agent that utilizes diary-like text to create videos. Diverging from generative AI models that create fictional content, the agent integrates audiovisual excerpts of archival content from Radio Télévision Suisse (RTS, the Swiss national broadcasting company) and transforms text prompts into a montage of historical clips. The Transaction then transforms the montage into a Manga strip printed by a thermal receipt printer. Each receipt strip is augmented with a QR code, facilitating access for a closer look into the associated full-length archival videos with context.

This work operates on an improved narrative-aware language-video joint embedding space based on deep learning, where text inputs are translated into vectors, and used to retrieve historical archival clips to construct a new video. The final Manga strips are transformed from the generated video through state-of-the-art image generation and style-transfer models.

Playfully sitting at the intersection of memory, history, and narrative, this work uses the dialectical and serendipitous encounter with archival footage to destabilise the fixed linearity of history and archival narratives. This transaction between private memory and public history aims to reveal the fragility, plurality, and absurdity of the accepted norm, calling for a reexamination of our perception of the past and the present.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Applied computing** → **Arts and humanities**.

KEYWORDS

archival art, creative interface, video retrieval

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1 INTRODUCTION

Archives, serving as repositories and catalysts of memory, assume a pivotal role in the sociological, historical, and cultural frameworks of remembrance. Although historically embedded, archives are not just about the past but about the future of the past [2]. Archives are powerful tools, they can affect what is remembered and forgotten in a given social context, shaping collective understanding and narratives of the past. For this reason, archivists, curators, and scholars have advocated the creation of more diverse, complex, and holistic archival practices for both preservation and accessibility [6, 8].

Figure 1: An example Manga strip, generated using archival video clips from an audience prompt.

The increasing volume and complexity require improvements on the access to and interpretation of archive materials. Efforts have been made to integrate computational tools to enhance public access to archival content by improving search capabilities and by augmenting materials in the collections [1, 7, 12]. At the same time, artistic approaches (such as archival art) leverage archives as media for creative exploration and transformation are becoming a powerful alternative. However, the majority of such projects focus on textual and visual archives, audiovisual (AV) archives, on the other hand, are relatively underexplored due to their sheer size and complex nature.

Most AV archive-based projects involve archival films that utilize or repurpose footage. Examples include *They Shall Not Grow Old*¹ and the *Grizzly Man*². These films follow a conventional linear narrative format for storytelling. Other attempts have been made to integrate participatory and serendipitous exploration approaches, giving rise to emergent narratives. Examples include the *T_VISIONARIUM II*³ and the *Sensory moving image archive*⁴. These projects usually feature an interactive interface that enables the exploration and re-edit of archival segments using limited and singular features such as colour, movement, and emotion. Our work, *The Transaction*, builds on the base of the previous attempts and aims for a more holistic and natural way to interact with archival content using natural language.

The popularisation of the encoder-decoder-based transformer architecture [9] lays the foundation for the success of generative AI like DALL-E and ChatGPT, and it presents new opportunities for artistic exploration of AV archives. Generative AIs are commonly based on foundation models trained on massive, diverse datasets that can capture semantics (or features) in various modalities (such as text, visual, and audio) with vector representation in a latent space. Generative AIs work in a way where they turn any input prompt into a vector in that space and use the vector (the semantics it holds) to generate new content in different modalities. On the other hand, by also transforming AV archival content into vectors in the latent space, *The Transaction* uses the input prompt vector to find the closest archival video vectors (the closer the vectors are, the more similar the semantics are).

Using text prompts that are descriptive and expressive of the day-to-day (such as sentences in journals or diaries), *The Transaction* facilitates the transaction of private memories and public history. It capitalises on AI's occasion hallucinations for the mismatch between the text prompt and the video fragment to create a serendipitous aesthetic moment. This mismatch reflects the nuance between the present and the past, the private and the public, the memory and the history, the reality and the absurdity. It is the hope that this continual shift in perspectives could cultivate a sense of "Inbetweeness" (akin to Brecht's "Distancing effect" or Shklovsky's "Defamiliarization technique". This dynamic fosters) and destabilise the fixed linearity of history and archival narratives.

Inspired by projects such as *The Short Story Dispenser*⁵ and *#selfie*⁶, *The Transaction* produces a receipt with key scenes and associated textual prompts in Manga style (See Fig1 for example) printed by a thermal receipt printer. While the video and related metadata can be accessed via the QR code, the physical strip allows *The Transaction* to align with curator Hal Foster's vision of archival art: it "make[s] historical information, often lost or displaced, physically present" [4]. The pixilated quality of the printed image colludes with the thermal paper to create an ephemeral record - the image is doomed to fade and the paper will easily mark and tear. The receipt, as a souvenir for the transaction of private memory and public history, is also a metaphor for the fragility, plurality, and absurdity of life itself.

2 THE ARTWORK

Figure 2: An overall example of the input and output of the artwork in different stages.

2.1 The Experience

Audiences enter any dairy-like text prompt from the keyboard provided, and the system will start to match the archival video clips using the prompt. Key frames from the clips and the original prompts are used to construct a Manga strip and printed through the receipt printer on thermal paper, with the QR code to access the video clips and the corresponding metadata. A detailed example of the whole experience of the work is given in Fig.2.

¹<https://nonfics.com/archival-documentaries-on-the-rise/>

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Grizzly_Man

³https://www.jeffreyshawcompendium.com/portfolio/t_visionarium-ii/

⁴<https://sensorymovingimagearchive.humanities.uva.nl/>

⁵<https://short-edition.com/en/p/short-story-dispenser>

⁶<https://tomstayte.co.uk/selfie/>

Figure 3: The overall technical workflow for Life Elsewhere. The upper part is the human perspective, and the lower part is the technical perspective.

2.2 Implementation

The overall workflow for the technical part of this artwork is shown in Fig.3. The following paragraphs elaborate on the key technical perspectives, namely how text prompts are transformed into videos, and how videos are turned into the Manga strip.

2.2.1 From Texts to Videos. Textual inputs from humans are truncated into sentences using NLTK⁷, then encoded using BERT [3] into input vectors for future use. The core of matching the human inputs to archival video clips is a narrative-aware language-video joint embedding space based on deep learning. To create such a space, a pipeline with the classic multimodal retrieval model MTT [5] and one of the most used standard datasets for video retrieval tasks, MSR-VTT [10] is used. All the archival clips are then also encoded into this space using the same pipeline. The input vectors are then used to conduct a similarity search for retrieving the most similar clips in the archive. The detailed configurations for training and using the joint embedding space are used as suggested by Yang [11]. The retrieved video clips and related metadata are stored temporarily on a public URL and a QR code is generated to access them.

2.2.2 From Videos to Strips. The key frame of a given archival video is extracted using the katna package⁸. Once the key frames are gathered, they are sent to a Stable Diffusion⁹ and ControlNet¹⁰ based style transfer pipeline integrated into a webUI¹¹ to transform into Manga-style images for stylistic consistency. Package PIL¹² is then used to add the original input prompts as speaking bubbles to the Manga-style images and construct the manga strip to print with the QR code.

⁷<https://www.nltk.org/>

⁸<https://pypi.org/project/katna/>

⁹<https://stability.ai/news/stable-diffusion-public-release>

¹⁰<https://github.com/llyasviel/ControlNet>

¹¹<https://github.com/Mikubill/sd-webui-controlnet>

¹²<https://pypi.org/project/pillow/>

3 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Utilising the improved narrative-aware language-video joint embedding space based on deep learning, as well as the state-of-the-art image generation and style transformation models, The Transaction can 1) generate videos using historical audiovisual archives based on the diary-like text prompts, 2) generate and print out Manga strip receipts based on the produced video, and 3) provide digital access and interface corresponding full-length clips and metadata from the archive. It aims to stimulate a more open and lenient interpretation of historical materials while addressing the intrinsic fragility, diversity, and irrationality in how we perceive the past and the present. Although this work is specific to the archive of RTS, at the core of this artwork is its ability to seamlessly translate any archival video material into diverse textual representations, and vice versa. Building upon this foundation, future endeavours will focus on the development of diverse interfaces and experiences aimed at delving into overarching themes within audiovisual archival art, historical narrative, and collaborative curation and creation using broader and various audiovisual materials for bespoke subjects and themes.

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